

Abstract:

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Near-surface, seismic investigations of unsaturated soils beneath the levees of the Lower Mississippi Valley:

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Flood-induced seepage under the Mississippi River levees poses an economic risk to industry, agriculture, public infrastructure, and private dwellings in the Lower Mississippi Valley. The primary foundation soils for these levees consist of Holocene fluvial and deltaic, unsaturated sediments. While geotechnical tests at specific locations are essential for evaluating soil stability, a combination of geotechnical data along with cross-sections of electrical resistivity and seismic shear wave data, offers the best potential for improving soil type estimations in these laterally heterogeneous sedimentary environments.

Interpretation of seismic data can benefit from insights gained through physical seismic modeling in a laboratory sand tank and novel theoretical considerations. For instance, in clay soils, stress calculations that account for soil suction between particles predict higher expected velocity values down to a depth of 100 m, as compared to traditional rock physics models. Laboratory experiments reveal that changes in P- and S-wave velocities during imbibition and drainage are sensitive to the size of patches of saturation. Laboratory experiments also allow us to correlate seismic velocity and attenuation to stress and saturation conditions in the near-subsurface, even though these relationships are non-linear. These considerations aid in the interpretation of areas with former levee failures and levee areas with unusual seepage.

To the south of New Orleans, seismic refraction P/S_H velocity models indicate variations in saturation and shear moduli beneath the levee. We gain additional insights into the soil conditions via inversion of seismic velocity profiles to obtain the soil-water characteristic curve, soil density and elasticity. We validate these inverted soil properties against field geotechnical data and the results of laboratory tests. Within the city of New Orleans, we conduct passive surface-wave investigations at sites that sustained damage from Hurricane Katrina in 2005 but have since been rebuilt. Beneath one site, the 17th Street Canal, a very low-velocity (Vs: 50–100 m/s) zone at depths down to 15 m, matches low-rigidity clays seen in geotechnical logs.

Seasonal changes in Mississippi River water levels induce variations in soil pore pressures in the nearby shallow groundwater aquifer (< 40 m deep). In a study north of New Orleans, at the city of Baton Rouge, we use time-lapse seismic reflection velocity data collected at the ground surface, to estimate aquifer pore pressure values. We interpret that the larger estimated increases in pore pressure mark those zones where the groundwater aquifer remains confined, whereas we interpret that the zones where pore pressure changes are smaller, indicate leaky zones within the same aquifer. Accompanying time-lapse electrical resistivity profiles and engineering logs provide a comprehensive 3D view of this site.

We anticipate that non-invasive geophysical surveys may become a standard and cost-effective method for predicting areas of high levee seepage. As with the oil and gas industry, the environmental and engineering geophysics community can benefit greatly from the geostatistical integration of geotechnical and geophysical data. The integration of engineering data and appropriate geophysical responses has the potential to improve our understanding of near-surface conditions in a more efficient manner.